

Responsible development of AI in European Union

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to give general overview of policies, guidelines and practices (projects) for responsible development of artificial intelligence (AI) developed and applied throughout the European Union (EU). Developing responsible and trustworthy AI has the potential to be one of the greatest aids in technological development, as well as human-technology interaction. Yet, it is also advised to be vigilant with the development of such all-encompassing systems that have high potential for innovation and transformative impact on society at large. Creating policies and guidelines for regulation and responsible development of AI has been one of the most important topics in the last few years amongst the scientific and legal community. With the rise of machine learning, innovation in the field of AI and uptake of smart technologies, that together facilitate the increase in efficiency and productivity of AI systems and AI-based solutions, there is a greater need to define stricter and more standardised policies and guidelines. This paper brings a unified overview, analysis and description of policies, guidelines and practices (projects) in the field of responsible AI in the EU. Also, this paper will include an overview of tools and methodologies applied in designing responsible AI, as well as an overview of guidelines and initiatives of companies developing and/or using AI systems and AI-based solutions within the borders of EU. Special emphasis will be put on the issue of high-risk AI, i.e. potential security issues of AI (e.g. ensuring privacy and protecting sensitive data), and the importance of making algorithms compliant to social and ethical values (e.g. minimizing or avoiding bias). Known potential defects of biased coding could be interpreted as a whole new threat to privacy and socio-economic rights of EU citizens, and the more common use of advanced and complex AI technologies could make aforementioned defects even more pronounced than they are now. Since AI systems and AI-based solutions, if not regulated, could have potential titanic effect on socio-ethical foundations of society, the importance of responsible development of AI should not be dismissed or negated. The approach to developing and applying AI systems and AI-based solutions should be based on vigilance, utter caution, transparency and minimal or limited risk., Future of AI should be in the hands of people who will ensure that this technology enables and fosters a promising and safe future for human society.

Keywords: European Union, responsible AI, AI development, regulation, policies and guidelines

1. Introduction

To be able to comprehend the guidelines for responsible Artificial intelligence (AI) it is essential to understand the concept of AI. There are plenty definitions of AI, some more precise and clear than others, but for the purpose of this paper most adequate definition is the one provided by European Parliament (EP) used in the “Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL))” that describes AI as “software systems that, inter alia, collect, process and interpret structured or unstructured data, identify patterns and establish models in order to reach conclusions or take actions in the physical or virtual dimension based on such conclusions;” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) p.22)

Another important view on AI is given by Luciano Floridi (2014) who believes that technology is not becoming smarter and more intelligent, but that we are developing AI and smart machines as purely syntactic machines, creating a semantic threshold between artificial and human intelligence. I.e. we are creating reproductive AI, one that is reproducing intelligent behaviour and not producing it. This is why human component is still necessary to complement and amplify AI. This idea is also supported by Nick Bostrom (2014) who believes that current AI is still inferior to human general intelligence. AI transitioned from science fiction novels and conceptual writings on possible human-like artificial intelligence, through first AI laboratories and projects as past developments, all the way to present capabilities and contemporary forms of AI that slowly became part of broader social, economic and political arena with politicians, scientists and decision makers recognizing the importance of developing AI systems. Giving legal frame to development and implementation of AI in open society marks great moment in history of human society. This legal frame requires coherent, strategic and collaborative development in order to maintain pace with the development of aforementioned AI systems. As it is often the case, legal framework restricts the speed of technological development due to rigidity of legal system. Because of that rigidity there is need to develop “A flexible and future- oriented regulation” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL))(p. 33)) meaning that the regulatory system should provide modern and fair intelligent algorithms that are going to provide healthy and socially inclusive decision making. One of the bases for the development of responsible AI is creating human-centric goals that imply inclusivity meaning AI would be developed to include all parts of society. Also, it implies developing AI on the principles of transparency where the system’s decision making is enabling users to understand way the systems made the decision in the first place.

Also, AI systems must be secure, and they have to use and ensure data protection Fair coding is also one of the challenges developers have to answer but the problem of fair coding is that it is flawed because there is no possible solution to not discriminate any part of society in any given time. Potential danger this regulation is trying to prevent refers to the flaws of system developer himself. Possible unintentional discriminatory decisions made by the AI system could have a major impact on discriminated group within society and could possibly halt the further integration of that and other AI systems. Within this hypothetical scenario we are able to comprehend the value of guidelines for ethical and responsible development of AI. Also, we need to understand there is a circle of responsibility in the developing of AI, developer teams are not the only ones responsible i.e. the circle includes all involved in the design, development and deployment of AI systems, from those writing the code and testing of these intricate systems all the way to those implementing the system, monitoring and evaluating its work and possible further building upon it.

Threats as weaponizing AI and other software systems became apparent in the last 10 to 15 years. Also, there are certain ethical issues like the implementation of AI systems in autonomous cars where they would be the ones to make the decisions of who to save or who to “sacrifice” in the case of an accident. There is no unified answer to that threat because the ethical AI as a science is only at the beginning. New progress in the field of AI and numerous examples of unexplainable decisions made by AI systems have spotlighted this branch of AI. Along with the evident risks and threats we usually refer to when talking about the “dangers of AI”, there are also more subtle ones, like biased decision making

in a health care system or a social care system where people could get or were discriminated based on the colour of their skin or their lifestyle. Today's ethical AI goes beyond Asimov's "three laws of robotics". One of the most evident examples of this is bias stemming from data selection and algorithmic decision making or lack of privacy stemming from the very same data selection and collection. Those are just some of the issues unique to the field of AI. This is why creating responsible AI systems and using AI in an innovative and trustworthy way can contribute to a more just and inclusive society

2. Methodology

The methodology used in this paper implies overview, analysis and description of policies, guidelines and practices (projects) in the field of responsible AI in the EU. Also, it includes an overview of tools and methodologies applied in designing responsible AI, as well as an overview of guidelines and initiatives of companies developing and/or using AI systems and AI-based solutions within the borders of EU. In this comparative analysis was used 5 different reports, two of them being commercial reports, two of them state funded and one was by the independent agency, also two commercial practical guides are used for the comparison and in the focus of these guides was implementation of AI into the businesses

3. Responsible AI development- definition and concept

From the dawn of AI, up to today, scientists tried to define the core concept of intelligent machines, and in almost every iteration of that concept for the most of its short history, intelligent machine was defined as a machine able to perform tasks in the way a human person would describe as intelligent. Human bias and belief that humans are the most intelligent species influenced the idea of what intelligence is, and also influenced the development of AI. The definition of AI mentioned in Introduction has left out the human part of definition, and that seems as a proper representation of these intricate and advanced pieces of software. Difference between human and machine neuroarchitecture indicates that way of thinking and coming to decision is fundamentally different, and the ability to exclude human intelligence from the concept of AI strongly suggest that our knowledge and concept of AI has gone really far from the humble beginnings of Alan Turing's ideas and concepts.

Also, the important part of the whole concept is way to determine if the machine intelligent, for many years we had philosophical Turing's test, the test where machine and the human are put one "against" other in the game of persuasion, and the result is positive if the machine has persuaded the human that he is in interaction with another human. Limiting these machines to human logic and intelligence is unfair to their development because as specified above, human and machine neuroarchitecture is truly fundamentally different, and accordingly to that it is only natural to surmise that cognitive processes are also truly and fundamentally different. So, the importance of differentiation from the human cognitive processes found in the definition provided by European parliament gives more room for development of AI in its own niche, differentiated and separated from binds of archaic conceptualisation. With this new point of view on AI developing teams are free to pursue new models of intelligent machines that are able of feats beyond our comprehensions, and also, even more important this new point of view enables other sciences to develop new frameworks and possibilities to implement these new technologies, and as mentioned above, new legal frames are able to form so development teams are able to make anthropocentric AI models that in their primary purpose have human society.

And with these new comprehensions we are able to act on development, provide model creators with framework and guidelines that are aimed to safely implement AI in our homes, cars, governments and other spheres of society. Goals of responsible AI development are defined by Virginia Dignum (2019,) responsible Artificial Intelligence is about human responsibility for the development of intelligent systems along fundamental human principles and values, to ensure human flourishing and well-being in a sustainable world." 3 And with this definition real values and principles of responsible development are rising, transparency and explainability, fairness and equitability, accountability, respectfulness of data privacy and data governance, robustness and reliability. These principles are core of inclusive and safe implementation of technology in our future and present, and should be explained to realize their value in developing of systems, and they are explained by 2021.AI's Responsible AI Principles (2021)

Transparency and explainability- these goals are focused on designing model that all included users, developers, shareholders are able to understand and understand the logic and cognitive processes behind decisions made by system.

Fairness and equitability- these goals are focused on minimising damages made by biasing of system and maximising fairness towards all human beings included within the system

Accountability- System and its creator should be accountable for all fallouts made by the system and should bear the responsibility for damaging effects encountered in use of system.

Respectfulness of data privacy and data governance- these goals are focused on safe and secure usage of data within the system, also designing a system that is going to be inherently safe

Robustness and reliability- these goals are focused on reliable usage of system, proper implementation of system into social environment with the ability to grow.

4 Responsible AI development in Europe

New European context of AI is built upon the principles of the Responsible AI, these open and forward-thinking concepts are showing the readiness to implement these systems in safe and responsible ways. The base of European context is risk, meaning that legislative framework is working towards minimising the risk for the end user, and holding model and model developer responsible to implement guides and frameworks for safe and reliable AI.

Diversity of the current guidelines and rules poses a risk towards society and the base of development of these systems is on their capabilities, and that is not anthropocentric model that is proposed to be implemented. During the analysis of AI programs in Europe, as described on webpage of European Parliament, three reports were made to build framework and guidelines for future European development of AI. First of three is report based on developing framework for AI that is fair and minimises discrimination possibly embedded in code; goal of this paper is development of unbiased AI that will treat all users equally, second of three reports is based on legal framework of development, the rise of unified and encompassing legal frame presents the base of responsible design of AI, third report is based on intellectual property of AI, and in its focus are works of intellect made by AI, and how to classify them. There are also reports of usage of AI in military and law enforcement usage, but system like those present danger and liability without responsible framework to work within.

Report of European Parliament presents AI system as high-risk technologies, as said in report “artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies, including software, algorithms and data used or produced by such technologies, which entail a significant risk of breaching the ethical principles set out in this Regulation shall be considered high-risk technologies” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) p.14), this strict representation is just an introduction into the next definition that gives modern and enabling framework for development, and that definition states “artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies are considered high-risk technologies, an assessment of compliance of those technologies with the obligations set out in this Regulation shall be carried out and monitored by the national supervisory authorities” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) p.29).

Supervisory authority is also defined through the report, and its definition will be noted and addressed, but some aspects should be addressed first, this anthropocentric model of regulation should not be left to the developers and model builders because there is high possibility that experts in those fields could work around limitations and frames of guidelines, also supervising cannot be left to the ethicists because they could disenable aspects of full potential of these technologies. Supervisory authority should consist of interdisciplinary team that is able to counterweight each member, and through that kind of cooperation full potential of this technology should be achieved. Supervisory authority acts as a governing body to oversee implementation of framework and guide lines in designing AI models, “artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies are considered high-risk technologies, an assessment of compliance of those technologies with the obligations set out in this Regulation shall be carried out and monitored

by the national supervisory authorities” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) p.29), also risk assessment by these authorities should be in standardised and unified manner, just as it is stated in report “the risk assessment of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies, including software, algorithms and data used or produced by such technologies, shall be carried out on the basis of objective criteria harmonised at Union level and in accordance with applicable sectorial legislation.” (Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) p.25)

After the overview of intricacies and inner working behind new European context of AI it is need to turn the focus on principles of responsible development of AI. Aforementioned principles of responsible AI are expanded, it has more focused approach, and that approach is based upon building the trust of public. This framework and guidelines have recognized the importance of public acceptance of these systems, and principles are more focused to build trust of society, and as mentioned minimising risks for end users. Principles rising from European understanding of responsible AI are ethical principles of AI, robotics and related technologies, human-centric and human made AI, risk assessment, safety features, transparency and accountability, non-bias and nondiscrimination, social responsibility and gender balance, environment friendliness and sustainability, privacy and biometric recognition, governance, supervisory authorities, reporting breaches and protection of reporting persons. As it is seen from this list there are many cross compatibilities within the two presented lists, and obviously European is more robust and includes more diverse aspects of development. Also, it must be noted that Europe aspire to be hub of responsible and safe AI development. But to truly understand what these principles mean they must be explained on their own.

Ethical principles of AI, robotics and related technologies- development of these technologies have to maintain the standards of ethical principles for responsible AI development.

Human-centric and human-made AI- this principle takes in its focus anthropocentricity of this framework, meaning that all technologies employed should have way a human operator can alter or halt the development and deployment of technology if breaches the ethical principle.

Risk assessment- this principle takes in its focus possibility of governing body to demand implementation of this framework in development of system.

Safety features, transparency and accountability- this principle in its focus has safety and security mechanism and plans that can be employed in case of breaching the principals of responsible development.

Non-bias and non-discrimination- this principle has to be insurance of proper, fair and non-biased interaction with all users, disregarding all disparity.

Social responsibility and gender balance- this principle has to insure access to all segments of society and social institutions to all members of society equally.

Environmental friendliness and sustainability- this principle in its focus has the ecological impact of developing and implementing these systems, it is focused on reducing its ecological impact through systems life-cycle.

Privacy and biometric recognition- this principle explains how the data collected by these systems should be protected in a secure manner and if the need arises should be used to maintain security of society in which these systems are deployed.

Supervisory authority- this principle demands that all members that are implementing this framework and guidelines should have governing committee that can ensure implementation of responsible AI

Reporting of breaches and protection of reporting persons- this principle in his focus has legal protection of persons that have reported breaches of ethical principles implemented in this framework.

(Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL)) pp.24-30)

Creating this kind of anthropocentric framework serves as a foundation for further development of easily integrated AI system in the open society, and the systems built on these principles have better chances to be trusted by population. The chairman of the committee entrusted with implementing these new guidelines and framework has perfectly defined goals and prospect of these new policies (2022), " Europe needs to develop AI that is trustworthy, eliminates biases and discrimination, and serves the common good, while ensuring business and industry thrive and generate economic prosperity." And from this statement are easily identifiable future plans and prospect of these systems in Europe, all-encompassing implementation of systems and digitalisation of Europe. It should be noted that basis of this future framework is not on limiting AI capabilities, as mentioned above the main aspect that is limiting within this framework is risk, and that risk must be assessed by the defined governing bodies.

On the other side, companies like Google, IBM and Microsoft are focused on developing artificial intelligence in accordance with European framework and guidelines, and during the overview of their it is clear that some of the principles are compatible with European principles. But these commercial guidelines don't possess the robustness and depth presented within the principles governed by European Parliament. In-house guidelines have technical side of AI development more covered and more refined. Human-centric model is proposed within these guidelines but it is not so broadly encompassing as these proposed within the guidelines of European Parliament. It should be noted that in the future governing bodies of European Union should insist on uniformed implementation of union's framework.

5. AI and society of now and tomorrow

The AI is possibly the greatest human creation in history of our species, the possible transformation of our society has made lot of people hopeful, and on the other side made a lot of people sceptical. The potential to fundamentally change our society in the ways that are unprecedented, from possible disintegration of economic system and "industrial revolution 4.0" to the breakthroughs in science made with using these technologies. Scepticism towards development of new technologies is not new phenomenon in human history, from the Luddites of first industrial revolution to neo luddites of today our society has always been sceptical towards revolutionary advances in technology and industry. Important thing to note after this sentence is that people are not aware how many jobs and things are done for industry by the machines, and still sceptics are adamant in their refusing of AI implementation in the society. Further implementation of automation of production and industrial processes sceptics have used to confirm their bias and is used to provoke fear and trepidation among members of society, also science fiction culture has made enough movies and series to make average person pose some import questions and doubts about intelligent machines and AI, and that is taken into consideration when European framework was taking shape. Instilling trust into public is the key part of successful implementation of AI in digitalization of society.

Indeed, AI without its responsible framework presents great danger for humanity, but building frameworks and guidelines to protect users has risen as possible solution for dealing with problems that unregulated AI could pose. It is frightening to even make hypothetical scenarios where corporations like Facebook, Google or other technical leviathans could be able to do with unregulated intelligent machines, from selling data to possible weaponization of such technologies, and that is just some of the more timid scenarios. Responsible development has become the present of our developers, and it is the logical step forward, and with such machines we are able to approach to new era of human society in safe and secure manner, automatization of work in these conditions could result in new renaissance where human society is able to lead life in a way that it would sound impossible within today's economical and scientific frame. The burden of responsibility lies on our backs, scientific community has to take action towards symbiosis of humans and machines, and being able to construct such frameworks as this one presented within this paper is important for transition to digital society. Legal frame for protection of users has also been important part of developing trust within the public, being able to be sure that end user is safe from any fallout being made by this kind of system is titanic

step towards safe society. Also, need for explainable AI is of paramount importance for legal system, ability to understand decision making process behind intelligent machines is going to promote fairness and inclusivity. And that is the future worth of dreaming.

6. Conclusion

Moral agency within AI systems has been an important issue since the dawn of AI. But as many scientists, engineers and AI experts agree, we still can't speak of full moral agency within the machine. The closest we've got is a functionalist approach to artificial morality. Having reasonable and rational perspective of AI's decision making and trying to link its 'behaviour' to intentionality, responsibility, sentience, consciousness and free will is likely to be a long haul. This is why the issue of AI ethics and creating responsible AI is significant for today's field of AI, as well as robotics. Consequently, having strong and clear policies, guidelines and framework is important for mitigating and managing risks. Of course, in that context, constant and systematic monitoring and evaluation of AI systems is of great importance. But it is also important to devise clear principles and criteria for designing, developing and deploying AI systems while avoiding the risk of suppressing innovation and technological development.

The future of development of responsible AI in EU is optimistic. If we implement guidelines and principles presented, it is quite possible for EU to become the main hub for developing responsible AI. This is important not just within the boundaries of corporate culture and its products and services, but also national culture and its trends like AI governance. The extensive, robust and unified set of guidelines and principles provides good basis for further development of AI and its integration into society, economy and politics. The duality of regulatory system has been evaded with risk-based approach towards assessment of future AI models. Being able to be flexible and uniformed will not hamper possible advances of technology, and yet it will provide homogenized ethical model for developing AI that is highly integrative. Focusing on security and safety makes these systems more approachable for general public, and instils feeling of trust toward the AI. Creating an opportunity for integration of responsible intelligent machines and software in society makes the idea of human-machine interaction trustworthy and less alien. Governing bodies should be formed with the idea of implementing diversity and interdisciplinarity because the concept of AI has moved beyond the field of computer science and has to be approached through other disciplines as well. AI's potential to make society more open, fair, democratic, equal and inclusive is noble and praiseworthy goal that should be pursued for the betterment of human society, but also with careful optimism that entails awareness of possible risks and threats. Since AI is becoming an integral part of our everyday life, our work and play, our economy and politics, we need to move away from simplifying the question of AI and human society through utopian or dystopian perspectives and think how would we go about building AI systems that bring benefits and possible risks, but allow us to successfully mitigate those risks through design for responsibility.

7. References

2021.AI. 2021.AI's Responsible AI Principles (2021). Copenhagen, Denmark

Accenture, Responsible AI, from principles to practice(2021).

(2022, February). AI rules: what the European Parliament wants. Retrieved from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/priorities/artificial-intelligence-in-the-eu/20201015STO89417/ai-rules-what-the-european-parliament-wants>

Bostrom, N. (2014). Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies. Oxford: University Press.

Dignum, VIRGINIA .(2019-11-04). (*Responsible Artificial Intelligence*). Available from: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=EEO8DwAAQBAJ&source=gbs_api. [Accessed on 29th Apr 2022.]

DRAFT REPORT with recommendations to the Commission on a framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies (2020/2012(INL))

DRAFT REPORT with recommendations to the Commission on a legal responsibility of artificial intelligence (2020/2014(INL))

Floridi, L. (2014). The 4th Revolution: How the Infosphere is Reshaping Human Reality. Oxford: University Press.

GPAI, Responsible AI Working Group Report. (2021-11)

PWC, A practical guide to Responsible Artificial Intelligence (AI). (2019)

Responsible Artificial Intelligence Institute. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.responsible.ai/about>